

Trigger primitive simulation-data comparisons and cosmic data selection in ProtoDUNE Horizontal Drift detector

Julia Favaro

CERN Summer Student 2025 (EP-NU group)

Physics Department, Università degli Studi di Pisa,

Largo Bruno Pontecorvo 3, Pisa, Italy

j.favaro@studenti.unipi.it

Supervisor: Dr. Klaudia Nicola Wawrowska,
Conseil européen pour la recherche nucléaire (CERN), Meyrin (Genève), Switzerland

ABSTRACT

In this project, I investigate the performance of the ProtoDUNE Far Detector by detector response between real and simulated data, with a particular focus on the Horizontal Drift (PDHD) prototype detector. Through this work, I have developed a deeper understanding of the detection principles of Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs).

My study focuses on cosmic rays, which are expected to be the leading high-energy background activity in the Far Detector of the DUNE experiment. In particular, I compare cosmic ray data from the PDHD in both simulation and real data, examining how the properties of Trigger Primitives (TPs) depend on the track angle. By quantifying these variations, the goal is to provide insights that could inform the development of future online trigger strategies for more efficient data storage of the most physically interesting events.

My analysis aims to demonstrate the feasibility of using collection plane TP properties to accurately identify track angles, though estimation of out-of-plane angles may require additional information from induction planes. The report addresses noise characterization and clustering challenges associated with high-multiplicity, noisy real data. Although computational efficiency may be improved, the findings contribute valuable insights for future online trigger strategies and data acquisition workflows in next-generation neutrino detectors.

Keywords: Cosmic rays, muons, LArTPC, clustering, linear regression, trigger

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1. Introduction

1.1. DUNE Project

The Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE)^[1] is a flagship international project, enabled by the Long-Baseline Neutrino Facility and Fermilab’s PIP-II accelerator upgrades, designed to address key open questions in particle physics. Its primary goals include precision measurements of neutrino oscillations over its 1300 km baseline, searches for rare Beyond Standard Model processes such as proton decay, and the detection of neutrinos from core-collapse supernovae, contributing to multimessenger astrophysics.

At Fermilab, a high-intensity proton beam strikes a fixed target, producing secondary pions and kaons. These are focused by magnetic horns, and upon decay, generate a collimated neutrino beam. The beam is first measured at the Near Detector (ND) to characterize its initial flux before traveling underground to the Far Detector (FD) at the Sanford Underground Research Facility (SURF) in South Dakota, where changes in neutrino flavor—such as the appearance of electron neutrinos and disappearance of muon neutrinos—are observed.

Figure 1: Schematic of the Long-Baseline Neutrino Facility at the Sanford Underground Research Facility (SURF), showing cryogenic systems and two of four DUNE Far Detector modules, whose current prototypes are hosted at the Neutrino Platform at CERN. Neutrinos from Fermilab Laboratory and its Near Detector will travel 1300 km underground to this site for final detection.^[2]

The South Dakota detector will be the largest of its type ever built. It will use 70,000 tons of liquid argon and advanced technology to record neutrino interactions with unprecedented precision.

The Far Detector (Fig. 1) is actually planned to have four large detector modules of liquid argon cooled to around 7°K with a cryogenic system. Two of these detectors have their prototypes at the Neutrino Platform at CERN: the Vertical Drift (NP02) and Horizontal Drift (NP04) detectors.

Both employ Liquid Argon Time Projection Chambers (LArTPCs), a detector technology that offers high spatial resolution and calorimetric precision. When charged particles traverse the detector, they ionize the

liquid argon, and the resulting free electrons are drifted towards segmented anode planes under a uniform electric field (Fig. 2). Combined with timing from consequent scintillation light, this enables precise 3D reconstruction.

Figure 2: Signal formation in a LArTPC. Neutrino interactions with the argon produce ionization electrons that drift toward three angled wire planes (U, V, X) on the Anode Plane. The two induction planes yield bipolar signals, while the collection plane records monopolar pulses proportional to charge of the electron drifted.^[1]

Figure 3: Top view of the ProtoDUNE-HD detector layout, showing four Anode Plane Assemblies (APAs) and their associated Time Projection Chambers (TPCs). Each TPC is mapped to a specific range of channel IDs, with TPC 1 noted to have a broken collection plane in the summer of 2025. Conventionally the X axis indicates the drift direction, the Z axis aligns with the beam direction and Y axis orientated upwards.^[3]

1.2. Horizontal Drift detector and signal formation

The ProtoDUNE-HD detector comprises an $8.5 \times 7.9 \times 8.5\text{m}^3$ cryostat, with alternating arrays of high-voltage cathode and low-voltage anode planes. Each anode-cathode pair defines a LArTPC drift region with a maximum drift length of 3.6 m. The standard DUNE coordinate system is defined as follows: the z-axis follows the beam direction, the x-axis is the electron drift direction, and the y-axis points vertically upwards.

Within the cryostat, four Anode Plane Assemblies (APAs) are arranged in two rows on either side of the beamline, creating four independent LArTPC drift volumes (see Fig. 3). Each APA has three wire planes on each of its two faces: a collection plane with 960 vertical wires and two induction planes with 800 wires each, oriented at -37° and $+37^\circ$ relative to the y-axis (Fig. 2). This configuration when combined with precise drift time measurements, enables full 3D event reconstruction.

The charge collected by the wires is digitized by cold electronics mounted at the top of the detector, producing ADC waveforms that record the signal on each channel over time. The induction planes are set to a voltage such to allow electrons to pass through, resulting in bipolar signals reflecting the induced charge as electrons drift by. In contrast, the collection planes intercept the electrons, producing monopolar signals with amplitudes proportional to the total collected charge.

A signal is identified as any ADC pulse exceeding the noise floor of the detector. For data processing and analysis, these raw pulses are converted into data structures known as Trigger Primitives (TPs). TPs summarize the key features of each threshold-crossing pulse. They are only a rough approximation of offline hits, as they do not have 2D deconvolution process, no signal calibration and no gaussian fitting. The main fields comprising a TP are listed in Table 1.

Since cosmic rays are expected to constitute the dominant high-energy activity in the DUNE Far Detector prototype, understanding how to minimize their data footprint for more physics events. The analysis presented here aims to support the development of data-driven selection criteria for background rejection, through angle differentiation, with the hope of contributing to the design of robust online event triggering strategies for LArTPC-based modules.

In Section 2, I examine the detector's response to cosmic rays, with a particular focus on how TP properties are affected by detector systematics—most notably the angle of the particle track relative to the readout plane—through MonteCarlo simulations. I evaluate a possible outline on how to estimate track angles using linear regression methods. Section 3 focuses on noise mitigation and clustering techniques for the identification of cosmic-ray muon tracks in real ProtoDUNE-HD data.

2. Preliminary analysis on simulations

We begin by performing a Monte Carlo simulation of 100 muons interacting with the PDHD detector and

analyze the corresponding detector response. For this initial study, I restricted our focus to the collection plane (see Appendix A).

2.1. Signal discrimination and detector response analysis

A preliminary step in event selection is the discrimination of genuine signal events from the background. The dominant noise contribution is expected to arise from radiological backgrounds, primarily β -decays of ^{39}Ar and ^{85}Kr , occurring at rates of ≤ 1 Bq/L. In particular, ^{39}Ar produces low-energy blips with a mean of 0.3-0.5 MeV/channel, which are in general separable from signal events that have a typical mean energy deposition of ~ 1 MeV/channel.

A practical method for data cleaning is the application of quality cuts on key TP properties- like TP_SADC, TP_peakADC, and TP_TOT (see Table 1)- correlated with the actual energy deposited in the detector. By studying the distributions of these observables, it is possible to identify background components and to separate them from cosmic-induced events, which produce a characteristic *cosmic bump* feature in each of our histograms (Fig. 4, Fig. 11).

Fig. 5 demonstrates the impact of a minimal cleaning procedure: imposing a TP_TOT cut of two ticks significantly reduces the number of background TPs, while preserving the overall expected event distributions as seen in the display.

2.2. Track properties as a function of angle

Inspection of the event displays (Fig. 5) reveals two characteristic classes of tracks:

- *Time-like tracks*: tracks entering the APA at a shallow angle deposit charge over relatively few channels but extend over a longer time, leading to larger Time over Threshold (TOT) values and higher energy per TP. In detector readout plots, these appear as horizontally elongated structures with enhanced energy signatures.
- *Space/channel-like tracks*: tracks propagating nearly parallel to the APA wires intersect many channels within a short time window. In the event displays, these correspond to vertical features. They are characterized by a large number of TPs, each with comparatively small TOT values.

These two categories represent distinct signal morphologies arising from track geometry, and form the basis for understanding angular dependence of detector response.

Field	Description
<code>time_start</code>	Time when signal first went above threshold
<code>time_peak</code>	Time at which the peak ADC value of the signal occurs
<code>time_over_threshold</code>	Number of time ticks the signal was over threshold
<code>channel</code>	The channel on which the signal was detected
<code>adc_integral / SADC</code>	Sum of ADC values ($\text{ADC} \times \text{tick}$) while signal is over threshold (expected to be proportional to total charge collected and proxy for energy deposit of our ionization particle)
<code>adc_peak</code>	Peak ADC value of the ADC signal

Table 1: Fields of the Trigger Primitive (TP) object and their meaning.

Figure 4: Distributions of key TP properties (`TP_SADC`, `TP_peakADC`, `TP_TOT`) used to validate the simulation and to characterize noise contributions. A distinct bump associated with cosmic-induced events is visible in each distribution, while the lower-energy component is consistent with background from ^{37}Ar β -decays and de-excitation gammas.

Figure 5: Event display of 100 simulated cosmic events showing the detector response in APA4. The vertical axis corresponds to time, the horizontal axis to wire number, and the color scale to collected charge. Left: raw data. Right: data after applying a minimal cleaning cut requiring $\text{TP_TOT} \geq 2$ ticks (500 ns per tick). The cleaning reduces spurious low-energy blips while preserving the expected distribution of signal amplitudes. Some events seem to disappear as they correspond to electronic tracks perpendicular to the readout plane with very low Time over Threshold per hit.

The main TP observables strongly depend on two geometrical parameters: the angle θ_y relative to the y axis and the θ_{xz} angle relative to the wire-pitch direction, as illustrated in Fig. 6. These definitions are conventionally adopted in PDHD data analyses. When a particle track is nearly parallel to the wire direction ($\theta_y \approx 0^\circ$), the deposited charge is concentrated on only

a few wires. As a consequence, each affected channel collects a relatively high signal, producing larger peak amplitudes. In contrast, when a track is approximately perpendicular to the wires ($\theta_y \approx 90^\circ$), the ionization charge is distributed over many channels, leading to lower peak amplitudes on individual wires.

A complementary effect arises from the orientation

with respect to the drift axis. For tracks aligned with the drift direction ($\theta_{xz} \approx 0^\circ$), ionization electrons arrive nearly simultaneously at the anode, producing a compact waveform with narrow time-over-threshold (TP_TOT). Conversely, when the track is tilted relative to the drift direction, the drift times vary along the particle path, resulting in a broader temporal profile and an increased TOT.

These dependencies are evident in both simulation and ProtoDUNE data. Fig. 7 demonstrates that increased θ_y results in decreased mean collected charge per track, while larger θ_{xz} values systematically broaden the signal pulse, as expected.

The key topologies of wire responses are also visualized through the scatter plot of $\text{TP}_{\text{peakADC}}$ versus TP_{TOT}

shown in Fig. 8. Tracks with low time-over-threshold and high collection charge are typically channel-like (corresponding to $\theta_y \approx 0$), while those with low peakADC and high TOT are more space-like (perpendicular to the readout plane). For higher peakADC, few TPs with substantial charge per hit dominate.

ProtoDUNE data primarily features cosmic muons entering perpendicular to the beam axis; these events are nearly isotropic in θ_{xz} . In contrast, neutrino beam events of interest are strongly aligned with the z axis, given our coordinate definitions. The marked difference in track orientation and TP properties is a powerful discriminant. Therefore, to optimize data storage and processing, cosmic and neutrino tracks can be effectively separated based on their angular parameters.

Figure 6: Definition of the angles θ_y and θ_{xz} in the detector coordinate system. The angle θ_y determines the charge collected per wire pitch, while θ_{xz} affects the temporal extent of the signal pulse. Simulations and heatmaps are used to illustrate the influence of these geometric parameters on signal amplitude and pulse shape^[4].

Figure 7: Dependence of TP observables on track orientation. Left: mean peak signal amplitude (ADC) as a function of θ_y , showing enhanced charge collection (“hill”) at large θ_y . Right: mean time-over-threshold (TOT) as a function of θ_{xz} , demonstrating systematic pulse broadening at increasing angle relative to the drift direction.

Figure 8: Scatter plot of TP_peak and TP_TOT for 100 simulated cosmic events. The color scale indicates the mean collected charge per event on the collection plane. Two branches are apparent: *channel-like*, with high charge deposit per hit and low TOT ($\theta_y \approx 0$), and *space-like*, with more TP hits at a lower peakADC and high TOT.

2.3. Track Fitting

Accurate reconstruction of track angles in cosmic ray events requires determining the slope of each track segment within event displays. Cosmic rays generally follow straight-line trajectories with minimal showering, motivating the use of a **linear regression** algorithm. To ensure robustness against the presence of outliers, the Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) algorithm is employed (see Box 2.3).

The analysis pipeline proceeds as follows:

- For each event, RANSAC linear fitting is performed. RANSAC regression is paired with RidgeCV—a regularized linear estimator that automatically selects the optimal regularization parameter (α) via cross-validation. Parameters such as residual threshold and minimum points per line are optimized using OPTUNA^[5], a hyperparameter optimization Python package.
- The fit quality is assessed via the maximum log-likelihood of inliers.
- For events with sufficient hits, the best set of RANSAC parameters is stored.

Figure 9 illustrates the results of this procedure on simulated datasets, where fitted inlier tracks are overlaid on expected true tracks depicted in bluish tones.

It is commonly observed that RANSAC-fitted regression lines are shorter than the full visible tracks. This occurs because RANSAC only fits segments of the track that meet linearity and residual constraints, excluding deviations caused by nonlinear effects or detector artifacts. Consequently, only the densely populated, well-aligned core of the track is treated as inliers, leading to shorter fitted segments relative to the full track length. One approach to mitigate this limitation is to identify and subsequently stitch together multiple track fragments in post-processing, determin-

ing the mean slope of our overall event.

RANSAC

Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) is a robust iterative algorithm for fitting mathematical models to data sets that may contain a significant proportion of outliers. Unlike traditional fitting methods (e.g., least squares), which can be heavily influenced, RANSAC focuses on finding a solution supported by the majority of the data.

The principal idea behind RANSAC is to repeatedly select a random subset of data points and use them to estimate the parameters of the underlying model (in our case linear). For each iteration, the algorithm:

1. Randomly selects a minimal subset of the data required to estimate the model parameters.
2. Fits the model to this subset.
3. Determines how many points from the full data set are consistent with this model within a certain tolerance (these are called “inliers”).
4. If the number of inliers exceeds a predefined threshold, the model is refitted using all identified inliers, yielding a more accurate estimate.
5. This process is repeated for a fixed number of iterations or until a satisfactory model is found. The best model is chosen as the one with the largest consensus set (most inliers).

Extraction of Track Angles

Let s denote the slope extracted from our fit, expressed in units of wire channels per time tick. The detector geometry is defined by the wire pitch ($p_{wire} = 5$ mm), drift velocity ($v_{drift} = 1.6$ mm/ μ s), and the sampling rate ($t_{sample} = 500$ ns/tick). The spatial conversion factor is $x_{mm/tick} = v_{drift} \cdot t_{sample}$. The fitted slope is thus converted to units of mm/mm (s_{mm}) and the reconstructed in-plane angle (θ_{xz}) is then obtained via:

$$\theta_{xz} = \arctan\left(\frac{1}{s_{mm}}\right).$$

To evaluate the elevation angle (θ_y), the endpoints of each fitted segment provide the spatial extents Δz (wire coordinate) and Δx (drift direction) expressed in millimeters. The total track length is calculated as:

$$L_{track} = \sqrt{(\Delta z \cdot p_{wire})^2 + (\Delta x \cdot x_{mm/tick})^2}$$

From this, the elevation angle is found by:

$$\sin \theta_y = \frac{\Delta z \cdot p_{wire}}{L_{track}}.$$

This approach aligns with the physical intuition that, while the linear regression fits tracks projected onto the xz plane, the elevation angle θ_y is orthogonal to this plane. As θ_y approaches alignment with the y -axis, the extent of the track projection onto the xz plane diminishes. However, the total deposited charge of the track remains approximately constant, reflecting a trade-off between the number of Trigger Primitives (TPs) and their individual charge amplitudes. Consequently, the estimation of θ_y is influenced by the ratio of total track charge to its projected length in the xz plane.

Accuracy is further validated by comparing reconstructed angles with ground truth values in simulated datasets, as shown in Fig. 10. Specifically, the *right* panel depicts the correlation between the estimated θ_y , which is derived from charge deposition per wire and track length, and the true θ_y . While a clear relationship exists, increased dispersion is observed relative to the in-plane angle θ_{xz} , suggesting that improved precision may require incorporating more comprehensive information, such as that available from the induction planes.

Figure 9: The *top* panel overlays all hits from 100 simulated cosmic muon events. For clarity I only included one TPC, to avoid encountering stitching problems between APAs tracks and imposed a timestamp offset for better visualization. The *bottom* panel adds RANSAC-best-fit lines for each track, using parameters found through Optuna and RidgeCV. The inliers (fit-consistent hits) are marked with a different colors, while the event they originate from our in light blue.

Figure 10: The *left* panel shows the correlation between the estimated θ_{xz} from our linear fits in the event display and the corresponding true track angle, demonstrating a strong linear relationship.

The *right* panel shows the relationship between our estimated θ_y , calculated from charge deposition per wire, for each estimated track and the true θ_y , revealing increased dispersion compared to the traversal plane angle.

Figure 11: Distributions of key TP properties (TP_SADC, TP_peakADC, TP_TOT) used to characterize noise contributions of real ProtoDUNE data. A distinct bump associated with cosmic-induced events is visible in each distribution, while the lower-energy component is consistent with background from ^{37}Ar β -decays and de-excitation gammas. For the rest of the analysis, I decided to use the TP_SADC cut at $1.5 \cdot 10^3$ ADC x tick.

3. Working with real data

When applying the analysis to real protoDUNE data, the implementation of quality cuts becomes increasingly important due to the higher track multiplicity per event and the elevated presence of radiological background. After careful consideration, a threshold of $\text{TP_SADC} = 1.5 \cdot 10^3$ ADC x tick, effectively excluding low-quality hits as illustrated in Fig. 11.

Prior to performing any linear regression, it is necessary to identify spatially and temporally proximate hits that may correspond to interaction clusters, given the inherent complexity and noise level of the data. To this end, I employed a DBSCAN algorithm (see Box ??) to label residual noise hits within the event. The optimal hyperparameters for DBSCAN were determined

through a parallelized grid search procedure maximizing the silhouette score of the final clusters.

This clustering approach faces challenges including occasional misclassification of intersecting tracks as a single cluster and cluster fragmentation arising from random background activity. These effects are illustrated in Fig. 12 where clustering results for three distinct events (with multiple tracks) are shown.

A practical strategy to improve track differentiation is to segment tracks based on their general properties. For example, separation by TP_TOT allows independent analysis of *space-like* versus *channel-like* tracks, while subdivision by energy—approximated by TP_SADC—can further refine clustering.

Following this, DBSCAN was applied event-wise to assign cluster labels to hits, effectively grouping spatially and temporally proximate hits and isolating noise.

Figure 12: Clustering results for three randomly selected events from run 32974 on APA3. The *top* panel shows the raw hits after applying a TP_TOT selection focusing on *channel-like* tracks, with timestamps offset for visual clarity. The *bottom* panel displays clusters identified by DBSCAN using optimized hyperparameters for each event. Overlapping tracks occasionally produce ambiguous cluster definitions, necessitating the subsequent linear regression step for track separation.

Figure 13: Example from run 32974, event 56 on APA3, plane 2. Hits are separated into *time-like* (on the left) and *channel-like* (on the right) tracks based on TP_TOT . The *top* panels display the original data, while the *bottom* panels present tracks identified through clustering and iterative RANSAC fitting. Some clusters exhibit overfitting, motivating the introduction of a maximum track number per cluster constraint to improve fit robustness.

Subsequently, the clustered hits underwent an iterative RANSAC fitting procedure, which employed once again OPTUNA hyperparameter optimization to maximize the log-likelihood fit quality. To prevent overfitting to noise, a final constraint limiting the maximum number of tracks per cluster was introduced. This iterative fitting method identifies linear track segments by repeatedly selecting inlier hits and excluding outliers, enabling robust estimation of track angles. The results obtained on the analyzed dataset are presented in Fig. 13.

4. Conclusions

Trigger Primitives represent prompt and concise summary of key signal feature for each hit of our APAs and serve as the fundamental building blocks of event reconstruction. Their properties depend on the angle of incidence with respect to the readout plane, which can present challenges but also offers an opportunity to distinguish cosmic data based on angular dependence, thus enabling more efficient data storage.

The majority of cosmic rays traverse the detector from above along approximately straight-line trajectories. In this work, I explored the feasibility of using linear regression together with Trigger Primitive properties on a single plane—the collection plane—to fit clustered hits and extract track angles. This approach provides a direct way to characterize angle distributions and identify challenges within the analysis pipeline.

The results demonstrate that the in-plane angle θ_{xz} can be effectively reconstructed using a single plane, while estimation of the out-of-plane angle θ_y appears to require additional information, like charge collection

per track length and potentially involving the induction plane. Although the presented method is parallelized, its computational speed may still be insufficient for near real-time applications.

Therefore, future efforts are directed toward developing faster implementations that leverage global TPs at the hit levels properties to establish an efficient workflow, which is essential for future online trigger strategies.

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Code availability

All codes used for data analysis and figure generation in this study are publicly available. The primary repository is hosted at https://github.com/JuliaFavaro//SS25_TP_ProtoDUNE.

The analysis presented here made extensive use of the following open-source Python tools: UPROOT (<https://github.com/scikit-hep/uproot>), AWKWARD (<https://awkward-array.org>), NUMPY (<https://numpy.org>), PANDAS (<https://pandas.pydata.org>), MATPLOTLIB (<https://matplotlib.org>), SCIKIT-LEARN (<https://scikit-learn.org>).

If the Jupyter Notebooks cannot be accessed through the repository, it can be obtained from the author upon request.

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Figure 14: Trajectory of a muon event (MC data) in time-channel space, as seen within the detector for each readout wire plane: plane 0 and plane 1 refer to the two induction planes, while plane 2 is the collection plane. You can clearly see that collection plane tend to have a higher TP_SADC. The jump in the first plane 1 refers to the channel stitching necessary to connect the tracks that are in different TPCs of the Horizontal Drift detector.

A. Induction planes

Induction planes detect the motion of ionization electrons indirectly. As electrons approach and then move away from this multiwire plane, the resulting induced signal takes a bipolar form.

Signals generated by different ionization events can overlap both temporally and spatially on the induction plane wires, which complicates the identification of individual particle tracks or hits and the interpretation of energy deposit.

Moreover, the induced currents in induction planes typically have lower amplitude and are more vulnerable to electronic noise and detector imperfections. This leads to a reduced signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), making the data inherently noisier and necessitating advanced noise reduction and filtering techniques. An example of the impact of this lower charge SNR and increased noise can be observed in Fig. 14.

For these reasons, our analysis will focus exclusively on data from the collection plane, where signals are more straightforward to interpret.